

NET-Fuels D6.3 deliverable 1st CD&E report

Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Report

Dissemination Level: Public

NET- Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES

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1st Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Report

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General Information

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NET-Fuels consortium

Short	Beneficiary	Role
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	CO
FRA	Fraunhofer UMSICHT	BEN
LEITAT	Acondicionamiento Tarrasense (LEITAT)	BEN
SUT	Silesian University of Technology	BEN
ITHAKA	Ithaka Institute	BEN
REACH	REACH Innovation	BEN
WRG	WRG Europe	AP

CO...Coordinator, BEN...Beneficiary, AP...Associated Partner

FOR INTERNAL DOCUMENTATION PURPOSES

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1 Introduction

1.1 Main Purpose

A comprehensive Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CD&E) plan is fundamental to ensuring maximum impact of the NET-Fuels project by supporting the outputs from the project (e.g.: deliverables and key-exploitable results (KERs)). Identifying target audiences and creating tailored information to engage and share with these audiences will put the necessary steps and actions in place to facilitate the future (post-project) maturation of the technology to pre-commercial scale and, ultimately, to full commercial implementation.

The initial CD& plan was delivered in Month 6 and this report is an update on this including all related outreach and exploitation activities.

1.2 Contributions of Partners & Responsibilities

WP6 is led by WRG Europe with extensive support from REACH (primarily for exploitation). This Work Package is also strongly dependent and interrelated to WP5 “Business Development and Potential Industrial Scale-up” led by REACH. The relationship of the Work Packages within NET-Fuels is shown in Figure 2. Work Package 6 overarches all the project activities.

Figure 2: Pert chart showing interaction between NET-Fuels Work Packages

The leader of WP6, WRG Europe (Mark Langley and Saule Kauneckaitė), are Dissemination and Communication Officers for the project and General Assembly (GA) with input and support from the Coordinator and Beneficiaries. WRG Europe oversee the CD&E strategy for the project, coordinate related activities, with REACH (responsible for the project’s Exploitation strategy) liaising with beneficiaries regarding industrial opportunities and exploitation of outputs, including protection of intellectual property.

All partners are contributing to CD&E activities. They are involved in more detailed annual planning and where input is required into digital media such as giving feedback on media layout (e.g. flyers and posters), video storyboards, social media strategy and posting, content for e.g. articles and blogs, and upgrades to the project website. Partners are also identifying relevant conferences, scientific journals, and trade/industry magazines to contribute to via articles, presentations, and papers. A log is available on the project SharePoint for all publications so these can be reported to Commission via the Portal as part of the periodic reporting activity.

2 Objectives and Expected Impacts (Updated)

2.1 Objectives

The objectives remain as per the Grant Agreement, and are as follows:

Objective 6.1: Develop and continuously update the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan.

Objective 6.2: Communicate the project results.

Objective 6.3: Deliver the dissemination strategy.

Objective 6.4: Deliver the exploitation strategy.

These objectives are being achieved through the following three remaining and on-going Work Package tasks:

Task 6.2: Communication activities (led by WRG) [M1-M48]

Task 6.3: Dissemination of project results (led by WRG) [M1-M48]

Task 6.4: Exploitation Plan and strategic actions (led by REACH) [M1-M48]

These tasks are associated with the two remain primary deliverables of the project, namely:

Deliverable 6.3: First dissemination, exploitation and communication report (M16)

Deliverable 6.4: Second dissemination, exploitation and communication report (M36)

The objectives and impacts will be achieved by delivering the CD&E plans, with activities shown in Annex 1. This high-level plan, which will be updated annually, is accompanied by a more granular short-term plan that will cover a 12-month period in the project (see also Annex 1).

2.2 Expected Outcomes and Impacts

The expected outcomes from NET-Fuels for which this plan is constructed to support and maximise remain as follows:

1. Validation of the industrial pilot in Year 4.
2. At least **1 Innovation Action** to scale up the system and prove biomass conversion efficiency to advanced biofuels at 55%, in connection with and a refinery/chemical park/district, bio-hub or industrial site.
3. At least **1 Innovation Action** to show the versatility of use of the component unit operation (interoperability): application downstream a biogas digester.
4. At least **1 Innovation Action** to show the application of the biobattery/P2G principle measuring the chemical energy stored by NET-Fuels.
5. Increased biochar production.
6. Improvement of carbon sink “Market” (new certificate emission).
7. Intensification of awareness for exploitation of the residue valorisation pathway for the prosumers target group.

Secondly, the estimated impacts from NET-Fuels for which this plan is also constructed to support and maximise remain as follows:

1. **25±9 Mtoe/year** of advanced biofuels production. Negative carbon intensity of biofuels: 80-110 gCO₂eq per MJ biofuels.
2. **6.7% ± 2.5% advanced fuel share** of final consumption over total fuel consumption.
3. **110±50 Mt/year of CO₂** of net negative emission.
4. **65±9 Mt/year** of biochar: massive biochar production reinforcing carbon conservative agriculture (CAP-Next Generation EU policies).

5. Advanced fuels costs: **70±30 €/MWh (improving EUSGAB estimate 83-118 of €/MWh)**.
6. **95-99%** of the biogenic carbon used in fuels and biochar.
7. Increased acceptance of advanced biofuels.
8. Increase knowledge of the technology deployment in medium-long term.

3 Update on Communication Activities

3.1 Target Groups and Audiences

The objectives, key exploitable results, and important outcomes of NET-Fuels are being communicated and disseminated freely (after IP protection when required) to inform target audiences of the scientific, economic, and social value of NET-Fuels. The following generic target audiences remain as:

- The general public: To inform them about the NET-Fuels technologies and the importance of advanced bio-fuels to the overall mix of clean energy solutions for transport and other sectors.
- Industrial stakeholders: To establish organisations (large industry and SMEs) interested in furthering the technology after completion of the project (e.g.: with future projects and -ultimately- commercial adoption).
- The research and innovation community: To establish organisations with a particular focus on: (a) research in biofuels, soil enhancement, and waste conversion; and (b) chemical processes capable of developing sustainable energy alternatives which can support the maturation of the project through to commercial demonstration and adoption.
- Policymakers and standards bodies: To support the necessary standardisation of chemical processes to allow regulated commercial application.

In general terms, the types of engagement for each target audience remain as described in Table 1:

Table 1: NET-Fuels General Target Audiences

Type	Target Groups	Tools	Type of Engagement
Project media creation and distribution	Industry and SME. Researchers. Policy and standards. General public.	Project Corporate Identity: Logo and identity, MS Office templates used as a common public identity for all management, communication and dissemination activities. The project logo will be implemented on all media.	Material: Project leaflet, promotional flyers for target stakeholders, additional promotional flyers for open events, scientific posters, project roll-up, project newsletters highlighting key results.

Digital media and social platforms	Industry and SME. Researchers. Policy and standards. General public.	A public website integrated with NET-Fuels activities, including informative content, news and events, video animations, and integrated social media accounts. The project will map appropriate communication channels, individuals and organisations, user communities to include in the NET-Fuels network.	Material: Digital awareness campaigns, events and networks to help redirect to the website where data and information can be accessed. Regular social media activity will also help to generate followers.
Scientific and technical publications	Researchers. Industry and SME.	Scientific papers will be published to inform scientific communities and potential users about NET-Fuels achievements. Publications will be through high-ranking, peer-reviewed multidisciplinary journals and more specialised peer-reviewed international journals. Technical papers and application specific results will be published in trade journals and media, targeting end user groups. All publications will be available via open access channels. Gold open access will be the default standard unless data and/or IP prevents this. In any case publications will be made available via public online repositories and the projects webpage.	Material: social media campaigns alerting target groups to new publications; lay summaries for industry and SMEs highlighting new outputs.
Conferences, Workshops, Trade fairs, Symposia	Industry and SME. Researchers. Policy and standards. General public	The consortium will define important international conferences to be attended by its members to present the latest achievements, to discuss progress, developments and challenges in this field, and to find new industrial partners.	Events: Such as EU Sustainable Energy Week, European Biomass Conference, and EUBCE. Also, to reduce travel costs the consortium plans to organise, where possible, consortium meetings in conjunction with these conferences Material: Project leaflets, factsheets, promotional flyers, scientific posters, promo roll-up, newsletter on final results.
Press and Media	Industry and SME. Researchers.	Press releases will be made at relevant points in the project such as interim results and key achievements, or for activities and events. Additionally, press and media representative will be invited to the final project PR event.	Material: press releases (EN), press releases translated by beneficiaries

	General public		
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Since month 6, some of these generic target audiences have been refined to more specific organisations through dedicated stakeholder mapping as part of the dissemination and exploitation activities. More information on this is given in Section 5.

3.2 Maximising Reach Through Partner Networking and Clustering

The stakeholder mapping activities discussed briefly above and disclosed in Section 5 have already highlighted several sister or related projects with whom NET-Fuels can collaborate. Some of these were able to participate in the Community Stakeholder Workshop held at Leitat in November (see Section 3.7) to discuss renewable fuels and energy. The stakeholder mapping will continue to be developed and used to create targeted communication and dissemination activities and events with a view to creating pathways to the next technological steps for the project, such as creating an Innovation Action project team.

3.3 Horizon Results Platform and Results Booster

Another key pipeline to support dissemination and exploitation is the Horizon Results Platform, which is available through the EC Portal. As the project progresses, the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that are discussed in Section 5 (and others that may occur during the project) will be uploaded to the Portal. These will then be accessible to other projects, researchers, industry, policymakers, etc., who might be interested in using the results for collaborative purposes.

NET-Fuels project subscribed to the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) on August 2023, with leading registration by REACH Innovation in collaboration with WRG, and participation on the coaching program by most of the Consortium partners by invitation. Specifically, the service modules used from HRB for the NET-Fuels coaching were the following (see also Figure 3):

- **Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy (PDES):**
 - **Module A**, Identifying and creating the portfolio of R&I project results
 - **Module B**, Helping projects from the portfolio to design and execute a portfolio dissemination plan
- **Service 1: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy (PDES):**
 - **Module C**, Assisting projects to improve their existing exploitation strategy
- **Service 2: Business Plan Development (BPD)**

Figure 3: HRB Service Modules.

Module A: So far, we have had a preliminary coaching session on the Service Module A for DEC, in which we were informed that we would have to build a group of other related EU Horizon projects (ideally 4 projects) to start the coaching sessions. Afterwards each project provided the needed background information about their DEC defined activities (pre-assessment questionnaires).

In order to accomplish the HRB requirement for Module A, 11 other projects were invited to compose our group, among them the sister projects approved together with NET-Fuels (i.e.: SEMPRE – BIO; Bio-Methaverse; METHAREN; HYFUELUP; CARBIOW; TORERO; FLEXI-GREEN FUELS; REFOLUTION; CRONUS; BIO-LUSH; CIRCULAIR). From the invited projects only 2 of them (listed below) decided positively to participate. Hence, for the HRB coaching on Module A, the following projects are taking part:

- [NET-Fuels](#) - Increasing biomass conversion efficiency to carbon-negative sustainable biofuels by combination of thermal and bio-electrochemical processes.
- [CRONUS](#) - Capture and Reuse Of biogenic gases for Negative-emission - sustainable biofuels.
- [BIO-LUSH](#) - Biomass Valorization for Sustainable and High Quality Fiber Materials.

Module A service is still running with coaching sessions scheduled for February, March and April 2024.

Module B: The Service Module B (DEC) is being managed by WRG.

Module C: The Service Module C for Exploitation (managed by REACH with HRB), includes coaching sessions about the exploitation of the potential results of the project, with detailed evaluation and characterization of its key exploitable results, exploitation strategy building, support for the intellectual property definition, and business models development. The coaching sessions concerning this service module for NET-Fuels started on September 2023 and is planned to be concluded up to end of June 2024. HRB has already given three individual sessions to REACH and has organized through REACH 2 open sessions with the voluntary participation of the consortium partners. Those open sessions dealt with the confirmation of the KERs defined by REACH with NET-Fuels consortium and with the characterization of the Common and Individual KERs and their exploitation perspectives.

Exploitation Module C service is still running with further coaching sessions scheduled for February, March, April, May and June 2024. Reports after main open sessions are submitted to the project by HRB.

Overall, the HRB coaching for NET-fuels has substantially been supporting REACH and WRG to confirm their expertise, as well as to enhance the capacity of the project to promote and exploit its technologies and project results.

3.4 NET-Fuels Branding and Other Digital Media

3.4.1 Project Brand and Templates

The project branding remains as per Figure 4 and is carried throughout all media and documentation shared by the project, including documents, presentations, and posters.

Figure 4: Project logos/icon and colour palette

3.4.2 Project Flyer and Roll-up

A flyer and roll-up have been created for use and/or distribution at events and conferences but can also be downloaded freely from the website. These media were used recently as part of the Community Stakeholder Workshop at Leitatz (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Project flyer (left) and the project roll-up used at the Stakeholder Workshop (right)

3.4.3 Project Animated Infographic

An infographic has been created by Fraunhofer to explain the overall NET-Fuels concept. This has been animated by WRG Europe and is available on the project website (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Animated project infographic

3.4.4 Project Newsletters

A first newsletter was produced in February 2023, which was a short introduction to the project and the project team. A second newsletter is currently in production and will be available by March 2024. These are all made available via the project website and social media channels.

3.5 Project Website

A dedicated NET-Fuels website (Figure 7) has been designed and built by WRG Europe (see <https://www.netfuelsproject.eu> redirecting to <https://www.netfuelsproject.org>). The website is managed by WRG Europe throughout the duration of NET-Fuels, and for 1 year after the completion of the project.

Figure 7: Project website homepage

The website uses the NET-Fuels colour scheme and makes full use of all branding. The website is the primary means by which industrial organisations, the scientific community, policymakers, and the public can find out about work being carried out by the consortium.

Since the website was launched in March of 2023, it has been updated with new functionality and content, including a contact form (for enquiries, newsletters or general sign-up for project updates), updated new feed and articles, digital media (flyers, and infographics, etc.), and a repository of public deliverable reports.

Figure 8: Updated project news feed on the NET-Fuels website

In terms of website traffic, the website had an average of **410 viewers/month** with an average number of page views of **1042/month**, peaking at 2048 page views in August 2023. The website already contains Search Engine Optimisation within its metadata, so traffic is largely driven by the content added to the website. All pages of the website are functional, so the project will continue to populate the site with news, articles, infographics, and other digital media to attract visitors.

3.6 Social Media

The NET-Fuels project is represented on three social media platforms: LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube, as follows:

3.6.1 LinkedIn and Twitter/X

At the beginning of the project, WRG Europe set up LinkedIn and Twitter/X accounts, which are also accessible from the project website. Currently the LinkedIn account has 66 followers with nearly 2000 impressions since it was created. The post that created the most engagement was related to the Stakeholder Workshop at Leitat. This is compared to 45 followers and 1200 impressions on Twitter/X, again with the peak post relating to the Stakeholder Workshop. It is acknowledged that engagement through social media is not at the level desired (KPI 500 followers per platform), but as more results and highlights emerge from the project, a concerted effort will be made to increase the overall following of the project through targeted posts and connecting with key organisations and related projects.

3.6.2 YouTube

The NET-Fuels YouTube channel has been set up within the last 3 months for long-form content and also to link from the website for all video content. At present, it contains the 3-hour recording of the Stakeholder Workshop held at Leitat, and which has been made publicly available through the website and social media channels. Further videos, including informational videos will be uploaded as more results emerge from the project.

Figure 9: NET-Fuels new YouTube channel

3.7 Workshops and Co-Creation Events

It has been mentioned that a co-creation Community Stakeholder Workshop was organised and held at Leitaf in Spain to coincide with the 12-month project review. The event attracted 35 participants from related projects and technological organisations to discuss renewable fuels and energy. More information about the organization of this event can be found in Section 5.4. The presentations were recorded and made available on the project YouTube channel. Also, a report summarising the event was prepared by REACH and made available on the Zenodo (see also Section 5.4). The event was for invited guests only, but the project social media channels were used to advertise the event for people who wished to receive the recording and event report (several requests were received by email to this end).

Figure 10: NET-Fuels Stakeholder Community Workshop on Renewable Fuels and Energy

4 Update on Dissemination Activities

Dissemination of NET-Fuels results is vital for the project to achieve lasting impact. Going beyond engaging target audiences and communicating project objectives and methods, NET-Fuels' dissemination measures will raise awareness of project outputs. These activities will highlight the importance of the NET-Fuels technologies and show how outputs can be adopted and exploited beyond the project funding period. NET-Fuels dissemination is tailored to generate maximum awareness of the project among industrial beneficiaries, investors, government bodies, potential customers, and stakeholders in addition to academics and research organisations.

External dissemination activities will engage those outside the project around key exploitable results, and includes user communities in academia and industry, and other stakeholders such as the public, policymakers, and government agencies. External dissemination will take three main forms:

- 1) Attendance and exhibitions at relevant conferences and trade events.
- 2) Open days and events.
- 3) Publishing papers in relevant peer-reviewed scientific and trade journals.

At present, NET-Fuels is not in a strongly "results-oriented" phase, so the Dissemination phase is in its infancy. At this point, it is more about creating the foundation to enable the dissemination later in the project, including stakeholder mapping and identification of key conferences and events.

4.1 Conference attendance and exhibitions

At present, NET-Fuels has not presented any key results at conferences or exhibitions. However, two (so far) have been identified for 2024 at which NET-Fuels partners will be present (and abstracts have been submitted):

1. XXVIII International Symposium on Bioelectrochemistry and Bioenergetics of the Bioelectrochemical Society 19th - 23rd May 2024 / Alcalá de Henares (Madrid), Spain
2. 3rd International Conference on Negative CO₂ Emissions, 8-21 June 2024, Oxford, UK.

Further conferences will be identified this year. An Excel file is available on the project SharePoint for partners to enter their suggestions.

4.2 Published papers

So far, one paper from the Ithaka team was published in GCB Bioenergy - 2023, entitled "Biochar from animal manure: A critical assessment on technical feasibility economic", publicly available in Zenodo via the link: <https://zenodo.org/records/8436814>. Furthermore, one abstract to each of the conferences identified in 4.1 have been submitted by partners Leitat and Ithaka respectively."

4.3 Open access and data management

Where appropriate, papers will be published using the newly established European Commission's Open Access publishing platform ORE, (see about ORE via: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>), Zenodo or equivalent trustful open repository as specified in NET-Fuels DMP Deliverable D1.2 [7]. This allows rapid, free, and open access publication, enabling others to build quickly upon new ideas, whilst maximising the

impact and of research outcomes to the Commission, the scientific and industrial communities, and the general public.

All data generated by NET-Fuels is centrally stored (for access and retrieval) on the project SharePoint using standard archiving data control procedures. Data is backed up on to secure areas of a central server designated for this purpose. Moreover, where appropriate, data is also be stored on the Zenodo open repository maintained by CERN. As specified in the NET-Fuels DMP, guided by REACH, data storage will follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) principles, which recognises the need to balance openness and protection of potentially commercially sensitive information. As such, all due consideration will be given to IPR, security, and privacy concerns associated with distributing project results prior to any external dissemination.

All data management activities will be handled by REACH within the WP1-Task T1.3. Apart from the DMP, one of the results of the work on task T1.3 was the opening of the Zenodo Open Science account (<https://zenodo.org/>) and the subsequent Zenodo Community open space for the NET-Fuels, via the link: https://zenodo.org/communities/net_fuels_horizon_europe_project/about.

5 Exploitation Plan & Reported Exploitation Activities

5.1 NET-Fuels Exploitation

As described in D6.2 (NET-Fuels Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation Plan V1.0), the exploitation plan for NET-Fuels attending objective O6.4 (O6.4: Deliver the exploitation strategy) of our project [1], the preliminary *NET-Fuels Exploitation Plan (EP)* was elaborated by REACH as part of its work within WP6 task 6.4 (T6.4: Exploitation Plan and strategic actions) and was embedded in this deliverable D6.2 (Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan) in month M6, organized by WRG within the overall work of the work package WP6. The EP will be regularly updated as required, according to the project developments, throughout its lifetime.

The main objective of the preliminary Exploitation Plan (EP) presented in D6.2 [8] was to define the exploitation strategy concepts for NET-Fuels, which considered among other aspects the analysis of the exploitation potential for the project results, in order to maximize the impact of the project outcomes, beyond and during the lifetime of the project. The EP presented the activities planned to ensure an effective exploitation of the project results, including strategic activities to promote the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to their target market. In [8] the preliminary NET-Fuels Exploitation Plan specified how the different tasks and activities related to exploitation will be led and structured, emphasizing the following aspects:

- The identification of the target groups more focused on the project's exploitation.
- The project's KERs, as defined initially at proposal level, which will serve as the basis for the initial exploitation activities.
- The exploitation strategy and how the different activities to be taken to achieve the market uptake.
- The intellectual property management.
- The initial plan for the roadmap to market uptake.
- The project's exploitation management and monitoring.

In the long run, the EP will further consider in detail the following features: (a) the identification of the Intellectual Property (IP); (b) the assessment of the expected socioeconomic and environmental impact of the generated knowledge and technology; (c) the identification of the possible technical and non-technical barriers to the exploitation of the project results; (d) the methodology and strategy for the appropriated management of the knowledge generated in the project and IP protection; (e) the analysis of the exploitation potential of the project results; (f) the individual exploitation plans including cost-benefit feasibility; and (g) the consolidation of an ecosystem of communities of practice for the project, including industrial partners

and interested stakeholders, aiming at promoting the project’s individual KERs and the overall NET-Fuels solution via the organized T6.4 exploitation activities.

5.2 Target Group Identification for Exploitation

The target group for the NET-Fuels Exploitation Plan is based on the one defined for the project’s Dissemination Plan (see section 3.1 Target Groups and Audiences), with focus on stakeholders that are more suitable to support the project’s exploitation phase. Besides the project’s External Stakeholders and Advisory Board members (ESAB), it includes large industrial stakeholders and SMEs, Prosumers, the Research Community (R&D international stakeholders and universities), refineries, agricultural and forestry sector-organizations, operators of biogas plants, automotive industry companies, plant manufacturers, high CO2 emitters (iron & steel and cement industries), chemical and oil & gas industries, wastewater treatment plants, as well as policy makers and legislature, national and regional bodies, NGOs, and organizations from private and public sectors at national and European levels.

5.2.1 ESAB

As stated in [1], [2] and [8], the Exploitation Stakeholders and Advisory Board (ESAB), appointed and steered by the NET-Fuels General Assembly (GA), shall be consulted within NET-Fuels implementation phase to facilitate the decisions of the GA and to provide advice on specific project activities and tasks.

The ESAB is composed of a representative set of stakeholders, including companies interested in the exploitation of biomasses, energy companies, research organizations and one refinery.

The main role of the ESAB is to provide guidance and advice on the exploitation and commercialization of the project outcomes, ensuring that they are maximized and disseminated effectively to the appropriate stakeholders and leading to greater impact and long-term sustainability.

Advisory Board Members

At proposal level, the international organizations (and network initiatives) listed in the table below have expressed interest in following the implementation and exploitation of the NET-Fuels project as members of the ESAB. The initial ESAB list, as in [1], is currently being revised and expanded by the project coordination team, as more stakeholders commit their interest to NET-Fuels’ development and outcomes.

REACH maintains within the “NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book”¹ (see section 5.4.2), an updated list of the organizations connected with the project (the NET-Fuels ESAB members), with their level of interest and engagement with NET-Fuels’ exploitation. Figure 11 and Figure 12 illustrate the ESAB Worksheet that can be currently found in the *NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book* online in the project repository.

#	ESAB Organizations	Country	Stakeholder SH / AB Member	URL	Main interest	Contact Person	Partner Contact	Agreement: NDA / Informal	Project Information level	Engagement level	Feedback
1	Cavite-EXTRA	Italy	Advisory Board (AB)				UNIBO	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
2	Botanic Garden (Research Institution of the Polish Academy of Science)	Poland	AB				SUT	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
3	European Biochar Industry (EBI)	Germany	AB				FRA (UNIBO / ITHAKA)	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
4	European Energy Research Alliance (EERA)	Belgium	AB				LEITAT	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
5	ENI-REWIND	Italy	AB				UNIBO	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
6	BAYERNOL Raffineriegesellschaft mbH	Germany	AB				FRA	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
7	SUNCOR Energy	Canada	AB					Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
8	CO ₂ Value Europe	Belgium	AB	anastasios.perimenis@co2value.eu	CCU/CCS Advocacy	Anastasio Perimenis	LEITAT	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium
9	Consorzio Italiano Biogas (CIB) CRPA Soc. Cons. p. A.	Italy	AB	http://www.crga.it	Biogas/Biomethane/H2	Dr. Mirco Garuti	UNIBO	Required NDA	Sensitive Info.	Invitation to interact with Consortium	Requested from PC / Consortium

Figure 11: ESAB Advisory Board List in the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (as of Feb.2023).

¹ Link: [NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Checkbook \(version for distribution\).xlsx](#)

The NET-Fuels Coordination Team is currently revising the list of the ESAB Advisory Board and will update it in the Exploitation Living Check-book in due course.

The Exploitation Strategy presented in [8] and reproduced here (see section 5.4) will control the way that the Exploitation Stakeholders and Advisory Board members shall contribute to the overall achievement of the exploitation results defined for the project.

ESAB-Stakeholder Members

NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community has currently a total of 44 Members (see Figure 12) and is continuously being updated by the Exploitation Partner (REACH) and other Consortium Partners. The inclusion of new members can be done by any project partner, by editing the Exploitation Living Check-book online via the file [NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Checkbook \(version for distribution\).xlsx](#).

10	Grupo Marca Ambiental (waste valorization group)	Brazil	Stakeholder (SH)	https://marcambiental.com.br/	Waste valorization	Álita Pavan	REACH	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
11	Centro Nacional de Energías Renovables (CENER)	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	vlopez@cener.com	fermentation of industrial flue gas, syngas	Vicente Lopez	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
12	Centro tecnologico CIRCE	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	alesandro.carmona@gmail.com	microbial electrochemical systems, bio	Alessandro Carmona	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
13	AINIA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	pgomez@ainia.es	bioenergy and biorefineries	Paz Gómez	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
14	AMB	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	jvalles@amb.cat	Metropolitan Barcelona	Joan Carles Fernández	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
15	TECNALIA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	soraya.prieto@tecnalia.com	Applied Research center	Soraya Prieto	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
16	CETAQUA - Water Technology Center	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	alejandra.cordova@cetaqua.com	water cycle, circular economy	Alejandra Cordova	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
17	Universitat de Girona, LEQUIA laboratory	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	sebastia.puig@udg.edu	microbial electrochemical systems	Sebastia Puig	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
18	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	Albert.Guisasola@uab.cat	microbial electrochemical systems	Albert Guisasola	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
19	IMDEA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	juanma.ortiz@imdea.org	microbial electrochemical systems	Juan Manuel Ortiz	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
20	ENGIE España	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	odel.goni@engie.com	energy distribution company	Odel Goni	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
21	SORIGUÉ	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	lborjas@origue.com	water engineering company	Zulema Borjas	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
22	ACCIONA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	marimar.mico@acciona.com	water and wastewater treatment	Maria Mico Reche	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
23	VEOLIA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	ignasi.gomez@veolia.com	Water and waste cycle treatment	Ignasi Gómez	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
24	Cluster Bioenergía Catalunya	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	mcortina@clusterbioenergia.cat	platform dedicated to bioenergy	Marc Cortina	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
25	Naturgy	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	jchamber@naturgy.com	Natural Gas distributor	John Chamberlain	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
26	FACSA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	ezuriaga@facsa.com	water and wastewater treatment	Elena Zuriaga	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
27	Depurador de Aguas del Mediterraneo (DAM)	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	silvia.donate@dam-aguas.es	water and wastewater treatment	Silvia Doñate	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
28	Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA)	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	august.bonmati@irta.cat	agricultural research	August Bonmati	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
29	BETA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	mabel.mora@beta.com	environmental research	Mabel Mora	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
30	Aeris Tecnologías Ambientales	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	o.prado@eris.com	design and manufacture of biologic reactors	Oscar Prado	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
31	ITENE	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	miriam.lorenzo@itene.com	Applied Research center	Miriam Lorenzo Nava	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
32	Institut de Recerca en Energia de Catalunya (IREC)	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	mtorrell@irec.cat	Applied Research center	Marc Torrell	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
33	EURCAT	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	frederic.clarens@eurecat.org	technological center similar to Leitat	Frederic Clarens	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
34	Tenicas Reunidas	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	rpericet@tenicasreunidas.es	Engineering & Construction Services	Ramón Pericet	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
35	FCC AMBITO	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	egonzalez@fcc.es	Waste Management	Enrique González	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
36	PreZero	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	egonzalez@prezero.es	Waste Management	Elisabet González	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
37	Agència de Residus de Catalunya	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	mvidal@agencat.cat	Waste Management regional agency	Maria Vidal Tarrasón	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
38	Bioplat	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	maragadegregorio@bioplat.org	Spanish Platform of Innovation in Bio	Margarita de Gregorio	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
39	Consorci Valles Circular	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	tzamora@ccvcc.cat	wastes management company	Teresa Zamora	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
40	Consorci Gestió Residus Vallès Oriental	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	ayats@creaduyvo.cat	wastes management company	Anna Ayats	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
41	Catalana de Biogas	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	ochebarria@catalanadebiogas.com	biogas plants development	Oriol Echebarria	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
42	FCC AQUALIA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	victor.monsalvo@fcc.es	water cycle management	Victor Monsalvo	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
43	VENIWIROTECH	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	patricia.ayma@veniwirotech.com	bioplastics from organic wastes	Patricia Ayma	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
44	TECH+	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	info@techplus.com	thermal electrolysis start-up	Diego Polanco	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
45	Repsol	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	pedro.segovia@repsol.com	Oil & Gas	Pedro Segovia	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
46	CEPSA	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	anam.castellblanque@cepsa.com	Oil & Gas	Ana Castellblanque	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
47	URBASER	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	efernandez@urbaser.com	Waste Management	Eduardo Fernández	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
48	BP Energía España, S.A.U.	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	jose.luis.garcia-broch@ect.bp.com	Oil & Gas	Jose Luis García-Broch	LEITAT	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
49	CENER	Spain	Stakeholder (SH)	https://www.cener.com/	Solar Energy Technologies and Storage - Coordinator of the RESTORE Horizon2020 Project	Francisco Cabello	REACH	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
50	SIMTECH (https://www.simtechnology.com/)	Austria	Stakeholder (SH)	E.Perz@SimTechnology.com	Simulation of Processes	Erhard Perz	REACH	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
51	BDI Bio Energy International	Austria	Stakeholder (SH)	https://bdi-bioenergy.com/	Greentech supplier of Biodiesel	Andreas Toth, Martin Ernst	REACH	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
52	IPT - Institute for Technological Research	Brazil (Sao Paulo)	Stakeholder (SH)	https://www.ipt.br	Research Development and Application of high-intensity technologies (hardtech)	Cecilia Matsumura	REACH	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events
53	IBE-USP - The Institute of Brazil Europe Studies (linked to the University of Sao Paulo)	Brazil (Sao Paulo)	Stakeholder (SH)	http://ibe.usp.br/	Research, Development and Applications (promotes projects between BR & EU)	Cecilia Matsumura	REACH	Informal	Public Info.	Information from Public Project Achievements & Events

Figure 12: ESAB - List of Stakeholders in the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (as of Feb.2023).

5.3 NET-Fuels Planned Project Results

The *Project Results* (PRs) identified for NET-Fuels in [1] were classified as Common and Individual Key Exploitable Results (KERs), based respectively on a common exploitation perspective, considering the overall solution of the project, and on an individual exploitation perspective per partner.

5.3.1 NET-Fuels Common KER

As reported in D6.2 [8], the overall common KER exploitation considers the NET-Fuels Integrated prototype with auxiliary systems, combining key-technologies for carbon-negative biofuel production, as well as its system analysis, techno-economic feasibility and market study to scale-up (see Table 2).

Table 2: NET-Fuels Overall Common Key-Exploitable Result

NET-Fuels Common KER
Integrated prototype with auxiliary systems combining key-technologies for carbon-negative biofuel production , system analysis, techno-economic feasibility, and market study to deploy the project at a higher scale (including densification and drying facilities for feedstock pre-treatment).

During the reporting period of the current deliverable D6.3, REACH has organized a series of meetings and workshops with the project Consortium, in order to define in a more granular way the sub-products and processes to be exploited from the Common KER. This is shown in Figure 13. This work has been done within the activities related to the “NET-Fuels Common KER identification” listed on the table shown in Figure 25.

Common KER Breakdown		
KER	Aux. Systems / Processes / Key Technologies	Main Project's Products
(1) Integrated Prototype	Feedstock pre-treatment (Densification Drying) / TCR / PSA / Oxy-combustion / BEM / Carbon Sink	TCR-Oil
		Biochar
		Hydrogen (H2)
		Methane (CH4) Heat

Figure 13: Main Products and Processes Breakdown of the NET-Fuels Common KER.

Owners of the NET-Fuels Common KER will be “All Partners” with the following planned exploitation routes and goals, so far:

- Validation of one industrial pilot based on project results.
- At least 1 Innovation Action (IA) to scale up the system and prove biomass conversion efficiency at 55% in connection with an industrial site (refinery/chemical park/district).
- Validation of the production of advanced biofuels with negative emissions.
- At least 1 IA to show the versatility of use of the components (interoperability), e.g.: application downstream a biogas digester.
- At least 1 IA to show the application of the biobattery /P2G principle to measure the stored chemical energy.
- At least 1 IA on energy storage coupled to one renewable energy production park.
- Increased biochar production & Improvement of carbon sink “Market” (new certificate emission).
- Intensification of awareness for exploitation of the residuals & valorisation pathway for the prosumers target group.

5.3.2 NET-Fuels Individual KERs

As reported in D6.2 [8], the exploitation per partner of Individual KERs is going to happen among the consortium partners in NET-Fuels, as they have their own interests and perspective on how to benefit from the developments, services, know-how and work experience gained with the project.

Table 3 summarizes the Individual Key Exploitable Results (KERs) specific to each consortium partner, as in [1], with initially defined exploitation paths.

Table 3: Summary of the NET-Fuels Key-Exploitable Results per Partner

Individual KERs	Potential Use & Applications	Potential Users
<p>UNIBO Assessment framework to estimate the environmental consequences engendered by the gradual implementation of negative biofuel technology from secondary resources. Negative emission accounting tools and related datasets and inventory database. System dynamics modelling to account for the use of renewable energy in power-to-gas systems.</p>	<p>Consultancy Advisory services Contribution to policies</p>	<p>Public sectors, Regional Bodies, JRC, ETIP.</p>
<p>FRAUNHOFER (FRA) Validated thermo-chemical conversion system at TRL 5 including oxy-combustion of TCR-tailgas, (production of H₂ according to standard (ISO14687) from TCR-gas. Production of clean CO₂ from oxyfuel combustion for downstream synthesis. Solution for internal process heating of TCR by process heat from oxy-combustion.</p>	<p>Application in combination with different biogenic gaseous fuels (biogas, pyrolysis gas, etc.). Enabling the use of biogenic gases for CO₂ based production of biofuels.</p>	<p>Refineries Agricultural and Forestry sector, Operators of biogas plants, Automotive Industry, Plant manufacturers.</p>
<p>LEITAT Validated bio electrochemical methanation (BEM) system at TRL 5, for CO₂ conversion to CH₄ at pilot scale. Integration of the pilot reactor with TCR and oxyfuel processes.</p>	<p>Enabling the use of biogenic gases for CO₂ based production of biofuels. 1 patent on pilot plant BEM technology.</p>	<p>High CO₂ emitters (Iron & Steel and cement Industry), chemical and oil & gas industries, Waste water Treatment plants.</p>
<p>SUT Validated CFD models of oxy-combustion of lean gases containing pollutants such as tars.</p>	<p>Biomass based conversion technologies. Biomass residues utilization. Waste to energy and waste incineration technologies.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations, SMEs community, Private & Public Sector, R&D International Stakeholders.</p>
<p>ITHAKA Carbon Sink certification guidelines for complex biomass conversion processes (co)producing biochar or other long-term carbon storing material. Know-how on biochar application in (fruit) trees.</p>	<p>Development and testing of novel biochar production methods. Improvement of biorefinery approaches. Promoting PyCCS by linking biochar and biofuel production.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations, Universities, SMEs, Private and public sector.</p>
<p>REACH Consultancy, Coaching and Training related to the innovation in NET-Fuels developments & framework and their Exploitation. Project development know-how to be exploited as a service. Research Data Management and Exploitation strategies to be exploited in further projects.</p>	<p>Engineering; Energy, Biofuels and Renewable Energy Sectors. Research & Innovation Projects; Private company development projects; European and Intercontinental project initiatives. New knowledge on negative-emissions biofuel production and CO₂ valorisation as services' knowhow.</p>	<p>Industrial & Research Organizations, SMEs community, Private & Public Sector, R&D International Stakeholders.</p>

WRG Enhanced communication and dissemination platform, Project videos, Project development know-how.	Engineering; Energy, Biofuels and Renewable Energy Sectors. Research & Innovation Projects; Private company development projects. European and Intercontinental project initiatives.	Industrial & Research Organizations, SMEs community, Private & Public Sector, R&D International Stakeholders.
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During the reporting period of the current deliverable D6.3, REACH has worked out with the project Consortium members new aspects related to the Individual KERs, as shown in “Annex 3: NET-Fuels Living Check-book – Individual Key Exploitable Results”, reproduced from the current online version of the “Exploitation Living Check-book” ([NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Checkbook \(version for distribution\).xlsx](#)). This work has been done within the activities related to the “**NET-Fuels Individual KERs identification**” listed on the table shown in Figure 25.

Detailed exploitation plans of the NET-Fuels Individual KERs will be further elaborated in WP6-T6.4, considering the results of the business plans to be defined for NET-Fuels in WP5, guided by REACH with the data provided by the project partners related to the individual KERs with their respective exploitation routes, directly updated online within the “Exploitation Living Check-book” (check section 5.4.2).

5.3.3 D6.3: Update of the “Exploitation Living Check-book

The current version of the online “Exploitation Living Check-book” file (Link: [NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Checkbook \(version for distribution\).xlsx](#)) was updated with the results of the final consultations and meetings organized by REACH with the NET-Fuels Consortium, considering the aspects listed below.

- In order to get a more comprehensive overview of the exploitation pathway, REACH has proposed a breakdown of the Common Key Exploitable Result (the integrated prototype) into the products generated by the process, including: TCR bio-crude oil, biochar, Hydrogen (H₂), synthetic methane (CH₄) and heat.
- The Common KER Breakdown was proposed to the Project Consortium during the 1st internal Exploitation Workshop, organized by REACH in October 2023 (see Figure 13). The Consortium also approved the selection of the main technical Individual KERs to be focused on within the Exploitation task. Figure 14 shows the selected main technical KERs, with the links to their original numbering as in the “Exploitation Living Check-book” ([NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Checkbook \(version for distribution\).xlsx](#)).

5.4 Exploitation Strategy

The Exploitation Strategy for NET-Fuels, as proposed in Deliverable D6.2 [8], described the activities planned to guarantee the maximum impact and value of the project outcomes, considering the related work packages (WPs) tasks and their interdependencies within the NET-Fuels scenario for its exploitation plan and strategic actions. The seven main aspects considered for the Exploitation Strategy are shown in Figure 16.

NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy’s main aim is to ensure and amplify the impact of the project results, in order to guarantee an effective exploitation impact both during and after the lifetime of the project.

For achieving the exploitation goals, the strategy adopted throughout the project considers the following aspects and actions listed in Table 4, reproduced from [8].

Figure 16: Main Aspects for NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy.

Table 4: Summary of NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy

Exploitation Strategy Aspect	Actions to be taken / Outcomes	Means of Achievement
1. NET-Fuels Common KER (Product Results (PR) and Key Exploitation Results (KER) Identification)	For the NET-Fuels Common KER, key-technologies and auxiliary systems will be identified and their combined usage within the KER will be specified in detail. Creation of business model (BM) and business plan (BM), with roadmap to market scale-up. Specific ownership and IP share definition and management. NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.	Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP6-T6.4; WP5-T5.1, T5.2. Discussions with All Consortium Partners. Workshop guided by REACH to All Consortium for PRs and KERs identification. Support from EC IP Services (IP Scan; IP Helpdesk, etc).
2. NET-Fuels Individual KERs (Product Results (PR) and Key Exploitation Results (KER) Identification)	For each NET-Fuels Individual KER, key-technologies will be identified, together with the partner(s)' background knowledge involved. Creation of individual (per KER) business models (BM) and business plans (BM), including market roadmaps. Definition of ownerships and IP share management. NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.	Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP6-T6.4; WP5-T5.1, T5.2. Discussions with Consortium Partners. Workshop guided by REACH to the Consortium for individual KERs identification. Support from EC IP Services (IP Scan; IP Helpdesk, etc).
3. NET-Fuels Exploitation Target Groups / ESAB (Continuous Identification, Enlargement and Networking)	Identification of the Target Groups (general and specific) for enhancing NET-Fuels Exploitation. Enlarging ESAB Members in terms of AB and specific international stakeholders. Synergies with existing R&I projects and related initiatives. Close relationship with NET-Fuels	Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5-T5.1; WP6- T6.4. Contributions from All Consortium Partners. Support from EC Networks & Hubs.

	<p>sister-projects from the call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09.²</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Exploitation Partner & Consortium interaction with Stakeholders via events organization and participation.</p>
<p>4. NET-Fuels Market Research Exploitation (Continuous update for enhancing exploitation opportunities)</p>	<p>Exploitation of the outcomes of the Competing Technologies & Market Research.</p> <p>Identification of the most stakeholders</p> <p>Evaluation / Analysis</p> <p>NET-Fuels Technology Watch Living Document (WP5-T5,1), and the Exploitation Living Check-book (WP6-T6.4) will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5-T5.1; WP6- T6.4.</p> <p>Discussions and Contributions with/from All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Support from ESAB.</p> <p>Support from EC Networks & Hubs.</p>
<p>5. NET-Fuels Intellectual Property Definition & Management (Continuous update aligned with the project development)</p>	<p>Definition and Management of the PRs and KERs ownership, protection and publication of knowledge.</p> <p>IP Definition for all Partners in relation to their PRs and KERs (individually or jointly owned).</p> <p>IPR Management.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5 (All Tasks); WP6- T6.4.</p> <p>Discussions with All Consortium Partners.</p> <p>Workshop guided by REACH to All Consortium for PRs and KERs identification.</p> <p>Support from EC IP Services (IP Scan; IP Helpdesk, etc).</p>
<p>6. Exploitation via NET-Fuels Stakeholders Network (Continuous update on the Networking procedures and on the Communities of Practice building for the project)</p>	<p>Exploitation of NET-Fuels' Stakeholders Network, in close alignment with the Communication and Dissemination Channels established in WP6.</p> <p>Input from (3) NET-Fuels Exploitation Target Groups / ESAB.</p> <p>Definition and continuous adaptation of appropriate Networking procedures.</p> <p>Creation of Communities of Practice for the project.</p> <p>Networking at regional, national, European and International levels.</p> <p>Definition of suitable KPIs for the Networking activities for NET-Fuels in total alignment with its dissemination activities.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p> <p>NET-Fuels Dissemination tracking records on the project's social media accounts will also register the progress of its networking activities.</p>	<p>Preliminary and Final Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP6 (All Tasks), with support from all technical WPs.</p> <p>Contributions from All Consortium Partners and their networks.</p> <p>Support from ESAB.</p> <p>Exploitation Partner & Consortium networking and interaction with Stakeholders via social media, virtual and face-to-face events organization and participation.</p> <p>Full alignment with the project's Dissemination strategy.</p> <p>Dedicated Seminars and Events.</p> <p>Support from EC Networks & Hubs.</p>
<p>7. NET-Fuels overall Exploitation Roadmap (Market Scale-up Roadmap and Leveraging of the experience acquired)</p>	<p>Exploitation of Common and Individual KERs based on excellence competition (Horizon Europe cluster 4 and cluster 5, low carbon and circular industries) and joint initiatives with industries (e.g. Joint Undertaking, Innovation Fund) at EU level.</p>	<p>Outcomes of the WPs-Tasks: WP5 (All Taks); WP6 (All Tasks), with support from WP2, WP3 and WP4.</p> <p>Contributions from All Consortium Partners.</p>

² NET-Fuels sister-projects from the call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-09 are listed in the Annex of D6.2 [8].

<p>throughout the project for further research proposals, publications and presentations at conferences)</p>	<p>Exploitation at regional level through ERDF and national initiatives, aiming at meeting Next Generation EU funding and initiatives. NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes.</p>	<p>Support from the NET-Fuels academic partners for the preparation of follow-up project proposals and publications. Support from ESAB. Support from EC Networks & Hubs; especially from the Horizon Results Booster (HRB)³.</p>
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Outcomes of the Exploitation Strategy will be monitored and evaluated via the target values defined for the planned KPIs to ensure that it is achieving the desired results. Adjustments will be performed, whenever needed, both during and after the lifetime of the project.

In relation to the first two aspects considered in Figure 16, a workshop with NET-Fuels Consortium was organized in October 2023⁴, in which the main definition of the Common KER in breakdown sub-products were tackled (see Figure 17).

Considering the Exploitation Target Group aspects, expansion on the invitations for the ESAB stakeholder-members has been continuously carried out, with the support of the consortium partners. (See Figures 11, 12, and 18).

Figure 17: 1st NET-Fuels Exploitation Workshop (Oct.2023) organized by REACH.

³ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

⁴ Recording link: <https://transcripts.gotomeeting.com/#/s/6773cdd83dfde8c7ac6cc96dfcf26dfdca832e10dbdfa886f1b72cb648d6e00e>

Figure 18: Exploitation Target Group & NET-Fuels ESAB Members.

According to aspect 4, about “Market Research Exploitation” considered in Figure 16, REACH is developing a Market Research Analysis, which counts with the outcomes of WP5 Task 5.1 supported by all related work packages (WPs) tasks and developments, and their interdependencies within the NET-Fuels scenario for its exploitation plan, as illustrated in Figure 19. Outputs from the work in WP4 will also contribute to this aspect.

Figure 19: NET-Fuels Market Research Exploitation.

In relation to the aspect related to the “Intellectual Property Definition and Management of NET-Fuels”, REACH has already taken pro-active preparation steps for the organization of the NET-Fuels IPR Workshop with the Consortium Partners, which is planned to happen within the 1st semester of 2024, before the 18M project meeting (as shown in the updated table of Figure 25). In this respect, Figure 20 shows the IP-Scan coaching session that REACH had from the EC support IP-Helpdesk initiative for Research Projects, in

September 2023. This seminar consolidated the expertise and know-how that REACH had to be able to guide the NET-Fuels Project Consortium in an updated way, for the definition of the intellectual property of the existing individual and jointly owned results.

Figure 20: NET-Fuels Intellectual Property Definition Efforts.

In relation to aspect 6, about the project “Exploitation via the Net-Fuels Stakeholders Network”, in November 2023 NET-Fuels counted with the organization of its “1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop” at LEITAT (in Terrasa, Barcelona), which had its focus on the Spanish Stakeholders Community. The 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop was co-organized by REACH, LEITAT and WRG; and has assembled a highly qualified agenda, which attracted the participation of 35 participants. Details about the pre-processing and organization of this event can be seen in Figures 21, 22, and 23. A comprehensive report about this event, can be found via the document “The 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop Report”, openly published in Zenodo [9].

Figure 21: Organization of the 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop.

		WORKSHOP: "NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop" DATE / TIME: November 9, 2023 - 9:30 to 12:45 CEST VENUE : LEITAT, Carrer de la Innovació, 2, 08225, Terrassa, Barcelona					
#	First name	Last name	Email	Institution	Description	Status	Confirmed
01	Ines	del Campo	idelcampo@cener.com	CENER	Invited participant	registered	OK
02	Kerstin	Steidle	ksteidle@leitat.org	LEITAT	Invited participant / Project Partner	registered	OK
03	Chris	Tuck	chris@wrgeurope.co.uk	WRG	Project Partner	registered	OK
04	Michael	O'Neill	michael@wrgeurope.co.uk	WRG	Project Partner	registered	OK
05	Federico	Ferrari	fferrari@acciona.com	ACCIONA	Invited participant	registered	OK
06	Nelson	Meclas Herrera	nelsonluis.mecias@udg.edu	UDG	Invited participant	registered	OK
07	Silvia	Bolognesi	s.bolognesi@udg.edu	EDG	Invited participant	registered	OK
08	Antonio	Giménez Lorang	antonio.gimenez@fcc.es	FCC	Invited participant	registered	OK
09	David	Checa Sánchez	david.checa@cetaqua.com	CETAQUA	Invited participant	registered	OK
10	Alejandra	Cordova Valencia	alejandra.cordova@cetaqua.com	CETAQUA	Invited participant / Speaker	registered	OK
11	Anna	Ayats Llorens	ayatsla@crecidusvo.cat	CRECIDUSVO	Invited participant	registered	OK
12	Odei	Gofi	odei.goni@engie.com	ENGIE	Invited participant / Speaker	registered	OK
13	Fatima	Dargam	f.dargam@reach-innovation.eu	REACH	Project Partner	registered	OK
14	Pau	Bosch	pbosch@leitat.org	LEITAT	Invited participant / Project Partner	registered	OK
15	Marian	Garcia	MAGARCIA@LEITAT.ORG	LEITAT	Project Partner	registered	OK
16	Simone	Colantoni	scolantoni@leitat.org	LEITAT	Invited participant / Project Partner	registered	OK
17	Raquel	Arnal Sierra	rarnal@leitat.org	LEITAT	Invited participant / Project Partner	registered	OK
18	Daniele	Molognoni	dmlolognoni@leitat.org	LEITAT	Project Partner	registered	OK
19	Mark	Langley	mark@wrgeurope.co.uk	WRG	Project Partner	registered	OK
20	Simone	Beutie	s.beutie@reach-innovation.eu	REACH	Project Partner	participation	OK
21	Gabriel	Steffen	g.steffen@reach-innovation.eu	REACH	Project Partner	participation	OK
22	Erhard	Perz	e.perz@simtechnoqv.com	SIMTECH	Invited participant / Speaker	participation	OK
23	Andrea	Contin	andrea.contin@unibo.it	UNIBO	Project Partner	participation	OK
24	Carlotta	Carlini	carlotta.carlini2@unibo.it	UNIBO	Project Partner	participation	OK
25	Diego	Marazza	diego.marazza@unibo.it	UNIBO	Project Partner	participation	OK
26	?			UNIBO	Project Partner	participation	OK
27	Andrzej	Szłęk	andrzej.szlek@polsi.pl	SUT	Project Partner	participation	OK
28	?			SUT	Project Partner	participation	OK
29	?			SUT	Project Partner	participation	OK
30	Nikolas	Hagemann	hagemann@ithaka-institut.org	ITHAKA	Project Partner	participation	OK
31	?			ITHAKA	Project Partner	participation	OK
32	Christian	Groves	christian.groves@umsicht.fraunhofer.de	FRA-UMSICHT	Project Partner	participation	OK
33	Martin	Meiller	martin.meiller@umsicht.fraunhofer.de	FRA-UMSICHT	Project Partner	participation	OK
34	Fabian (?)	Stenzel	fabian.stenzel@umsicht.fraunhofer.de	FRA-UMSICHT	Project Partner	participation	OK
35	Antonio	Sánchez	asgova@ctingenieros.es	Cluster Bioenergia University of Girona	Invited participant / Speaker	participation	OK
36	Luis Rafael	Lopez	luisrafael.lopez@udg.edu	University of Girona	Invited participant / Speaker	participation	OK

Figure 22: List of Participants of the 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop.

NET-Fuels
Increasing Biomass Conversion Efficiency to Carbon-Negative Sustainable Biofuels by Combination of Thermochemical and Bio-Electrochemical Processes
<https://www.netfuelsproject.org/>

WORKSHOP: "NET-Fuels 1st Stakeholders Community Workshop"
DATE / TIME: **November 9, 2023 - 9:30 to 12:45 CEST**
VENUE : **LEITAT, Carrer de la Innovació, 2, 08225, Terrassa, Barcelona**

ORGANIZERS: [LEITAT](#) (Host; NET-Fuels Development Partner); [REACH](#) (NET-Fuels Exploitation Partner); [WRG](#) (NET-Fuels Dissemination Partner)
COLLABORATION: All NET-Fuels Partners (<https://www.netfuelsproject.org/about.html>)

WORKSHOP AGENDA:

9:30 - 9:40: Opening act by event host (Eduard Borràs, [LEITAT](#)) and co-organizers (Fatima Dargam, [REACH](#) & Mark Langley, [WRG](#))
9:40 - 10:10: Summary Presentation of the NET-Fuels Project Concept / Partners Roles / Estimated Results (Andrea Contin, [UNIBO](#))
10:10 - 10:50: Presentation of the NET-Fuels Technologies (Christian Groves, [FRA](#) & Daniele Molognoni, [LEITAT](#))
10:50 - 11:00: Comments and Questions & Answers about NET-Fuels
11:00 - 11:15: Coffee Break
11:15 - 12:30: Presentations from invited Stakeholders (slots of 15 minutes)
11:15 - 11:30: Antonio Sánchez / [Cluster Bioenergia Catalunya](#): "Biofuels and derivatives projects in the current Oil & Gas industry"
11:30 - 11:45: Alejandra Cordova / [CETAQUA](#): "[SEMPRE-BIO](#), new cost-effective solutions to produce Biomethane"
11:45 - 12:00: Odei Goñi / [ENGIE Spain](#): "The [REGENERA project](#): development of hybrid energy storage technologies and predictive models to transform industries into decentralized points for renewable energy management"
12:00 - 12:15: Luis Rafael Lopez / [University of Girona](#): "Indoor CO2 as renewable carbon source: Coupling indoor CO2 direct air capture to microbial electrosynthesis technologies"
12:15 - 12:30: Erhard Perz / [SIMTECH](#): "Simulation of virtual use-cases for the research project [RESTORE](#) using the web-based process simulation platform [JPSE GO](#)"
12:30 - 12:45: Q&A - Open Discussions - Workshop Closing Session by project coordinator ([UNIBO](#)), event host ([LEITAT](#)) and co-organizers ([REACH](#) & [WRG](#))
12:45: Buffet & Networking

NET-Fuels Project Consortium warmly thanks the external guests for their participation and potential feedback!

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Figure 23: Agenda of the 1st NET-Fuels Stakeholders Community Workshop.

In relation to the last aspect in Figure 16 about the outcome of the "Overall NET-Fuels Exploitation Roadmap", the efforts that are being taken by REACH with the support of the Horizon Results Booster Coaching sessions, involving the NET-Fuels Consortium Partners, will be considered so that a realistic and feasible exploitation roadmap for the project can be produced. As indicated in Figure 24, the *NET-Fuels Overall Exploitation Roadmap* will also be based on the outcomes of the Market Analysis for Exploitation, the Key Exploitable Results (KERS) Business Models, and the final NET-Fuels Business Plan (in relation to its Common Exploitable Result).

5.4.2 NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book

As stated in D6.2 [8], REACH shared with the Consortium a living document named “NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book”, in month M7 via the project SharePoint repository, including: the overall *Project Results* and the identified *Key Exploitable Results (KERs)*, also related to the partners background knowledge for their developments. Link: [NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Checkbook \(version for distribution\).xlsx](#).

One of the objectives of the online NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book is to collect inputs from all project partners, regarding updates and fine-tuning of the definitions of the Project Results, the Exploitable Results (KERs), and the Intellectual Property (IP). The Exploitation Check-book records the evolution of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy’s development as a whole through its actions and outcomes. It also maintains an updated list of the organizations connected with the project (within the ESAB), including their level of interest and engagement with NET-Fuels’ exploitation.

Figures 26 and 27 show screenshots of the updated NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book.

NET-Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES
HORIZON-CL5-2021-03-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101082780

Definitions / Guide to use the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book
How to identify BG, PRs and KERs?

Background (BG)
 _Pre-existing know-how before entering the project
 _A "Background" has to either be:
 a) relevant to the own project result(s),
 b) necessary to carry out/implement the NET-Fuels project in general, or
 c) relevant for other consortium partners to achieve their project results.

Project Results (PRs)
 _Results - including information - which are generated under the project (being protectable or not)
 _A PR belongs to the beneficiary generating it.
 - PRs can be jointly generated (joint ownership) and can be transferred (third parties).

Request to NET-Fuels Partners:
 - Fill in the **Project Results (PRs)** related to your development
 - Fill in / Check and Add-on the **Key-Exploitable Results (KERs)**
 - Fill in the **Background (BG)** related to your know-how and to the project implementation

Key-Exploitable Results (KERs)

USE:
 - Direct or Indirect utilisation of Project Results beyond project scope.
 - In further research activities (other than those covered by the project) or for developing, creating and marketing a product, a process or a service.

KER:
 - An Exploitable Result is defined as an outcome of the project (achieved or expected) that meets two conditions:
 - It can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result (product, process, service, etc.) (a patent for licensing is also an exploitable result)
 - It has commercial/social/academic relevance

_Exploitable results might need further R&D, prototyping, engineering, validation, etc. at the end of the project before they become commercially exploitable. They are generally defined as products, processes, services, methods, etc., which are new, improved or more efficient than existing ones.

Figure 26: Screenshot Detail of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (Guide for Usage).

NET-Fuels | INCREASING BIOMASS CONVERSION EFFICIENCY TO CARBON-NEGATIVE SUSTAINABLE BIOFUELS BY COMBINATION OF THERMOCHEMICAL AND BIO-ELECTROCHEMICAL PROCESSES
HORIZON-CL5-2021-03-03-09 | GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER: 101082780

Updated Version in SharePoint November 2023

Project's Products / Process	Potential Enablers	Potential Applications	Benefits for Users	USP (Unique Selling Proposition)	Main Competitors
TCR-Oil (crude oil)	Petro-Chemical industries; Ethanol distribution companies; Automotive industry; Marine industry; Refineries for co-processing of the oil; Polysiloxane Power Systems AG; MMH Diesel; Turbo Comets Inc.; Caterpillar; Wärtsilä; Ineo; Linde/air; EMP/VERSALIS; Ethanol refiners; Aviation sector; Biorefiners Distributors with post-processing competence; "Traditional" biochar companies / operators of pyrolysis units that focus on supplying heat to district heating grids; some companies try to store pyrolysis oil geologically	Production of biofuel (HDO and distillation) for vehicles; Use as a marine fuel; Production of standardized gasoline and diesel; Chemical precursors; Transportation CO2-negative energy pathway; Road, Rail, Agriculture, Marine, Aviation; Direct route for governments to reduce CO2 emissions; District heating in winter; Fuels for shipping; Refined (HDO) Fuels for individual mobility and aviation; Production of Diesel / BioFuel; Transportation sector	Energy Security; Less corporate marketing risk of 3rd party CO2 certificates having a long-term negative effect on the environment and climate; (Less exposure to greenwashing); CO2-negative energy storage for mobile use; Independent from fossil crude oil import; Reduction of CO2 emissions by substitution of fossil crude oil; TCR-Fuels may not be affected by fuel bans in some sectors; Use of Fuel generated with CO2-negative system	Increase in energy security; TCR oil can be co-processed in a refinery, because of its thermal stability; Storable pyrolysis oil approved for use as fuel <=> so far not provided for biomass; Adds value via its "green" generation within NET-Fuels	Energy crops, such as ethanol blends; Fast pyrolysis processes; a higher oil price oil quality is poor. Further processing is also https://www.mckel.de/index.php; BioFuels Production Companies; Plastics which process used tires, plastics etc. https://www.vowasa.com/four-brands/biogas; pyrolysis oil separation at industrial scale; plastics; Biomass-based isocyanates of Biog pyrolysis gas who condensation the oil; Bio-refiners; Competitors for the feedstock; Other industries which use the same raw material to pay higher prices

Navigation: Guide | PRs | All KERs | **Common KER (breakdown)** | Individual KERs | BG | ESAB | TF

Figure 27: Screenshot Detail of one sheet of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book (updated version).

The data within the Exploitation Check-book embed the information of the project Grant Agreement (GA) with small refinements, including all partners' review and add-ons, filtering and expanding on the preliminary list of the project's results and KERs.

During the exploitation workshops guided by REACH, each partner is requested to include inputs regarding the KERs, among others, like: the Technical Readiness Levels (TRL) of the project results (current and expected TRLs), details of the products' ownership (individually-owned, jointly-owned), relevant information for the definition of the exploitation pathway (open, licensed, patents, etc.). The NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book is essential for the implementation of the Intellectual Property Strategy for the project.

5.4.3 Networking Activities

Besides the Networking and Clustering activities mentioned in the Communication and Dissemination Plan, the Exploitation will also profit on excellence competition (Horizon Europe cluster 4 and cluster 5, low carbon and circular industries) and joint initiatives with industries (e.g.: Joint Undertakings⁵ and Innovation Fund⁶, among others), and at regional level through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)⁷ and related National initiatives, aiming at meeting Next Generation EU⁸ funding and initiatives, as planned in [1]. Academic partners will leverage the experience acquired throughout the project for further research proposals, publications, and presentations at conferences.

For the ESAB members, dedicated meetings will be set up after month M13 with selected Stakeholders and Advisory Board members for the definition of the project's Common KER Business Plan.

As defined in [8], for the Exploitation Strategy the following will be carried out in terms of networking activities:

- The Exploitation partner (REACH) will enforce that networking interactions among Consortium members and Stakeholders regularly happen via social media, as well as via virtual and face-to-face events organization and participation. This will be organized in full alignment with the project's dissemination strategy. Dedicated Seminars and Events with Stakeholders have already started to be organized as planned in [1] (see [9]).
- REACH will cater for the definition and continuous adaptation of appropriate Networking procedures for NET-Fuels, with the creation of Communities of Practice for the project. Networking at regional, national, European and International levels will be encouraged and targeted, following suitably defined KPIs for the Networking activities for NET-Fuels in total alignment with the dissemination tasks.
- The Exploitation Task T6.4 has already started to establish an ecosystem of communities of practice for the project, including industrial partners and interested stakeholders, aiming at promoting the project's identified KERs and disseminating their validation via the represented case studies, so that other interested stakeholders will be able to further engage with the NET-Fuels solution via the organized T6.4 exploitation activities.

The NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will record the development of this action and its outcomes, and the project's Dissemination tracking records on the project's social media accounts will also register the progress of its networking activities on a regular basis.

⁵ Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe: <https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vlgkodah31yz>

⁶ Innovation Fund: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund_en

⁷ ERDF: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en

⁸ Next Generation EU: https://next-generation-eu.europa.eu/index_en

5.4.4 Intellectual Property Management

As planned in [8], for the NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy (item 5), a detailed Intellectual Property Management description will be provided, aiming to inform the partners about the importance of protecting the project generated data, both individually and collectively.

A specific methodology and strategy in support of the definition and management of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and Protection within the NET-Fuels project has been defined by REACH customized for NET-Fuels, and will be explained to the Project Consortium during the co-creation of the IP definitions with relation to the KERs in the activities related to the “NET-Fuels Intellectual Property definition”, planned for the 1st semester of 2024. This workshop will embed the following agenda:

- Legal frame for IP Management in NET-Fuels (What is the legal setup for exploitation in the project?).
- KER Ownership (Which partner can call a result “their own”?).
- Protection of Results (How can a project result be protected in practice?).
- Access Rights (What are the options for exploiting results beyond the project’s lifetime?).
- Upcoming Exploitation Activities relating to IP management.

Details about the IP definition will be reported in the next version of the NET-Fuels Exploitation Report, incorporating individual exploitation plans for all KERs (per partner).

IP Activities with the NET-Fuels Consortium: A Workshop is planned, led by REACH, as the “NET-Fuels Intellectual Property definition” event listed on the table shown in Figure 25, to align and strengthen the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) topic among the Consortium. IPR support services from the EC - European Commission, like IP-Scan within the EC IP Helpdesk⁹, are also encouraged to be followed/undertaken by NET-Fuels project partners. The IP Workshop with the Project Consortium was initially planned for November 2023, but REACH decided to postpone it to April 2024, due to the development of the Exploitation coaching from the Horizon Results Booster (see Figure 25).

5.5 Roadmap to Market Uptake

For NET-Fuels Exploitation, all tasks from WP5, which include: the Technology Watch, Market Analysis, Business Model and Business Plan Development, Regulatory Assessment and System Scale-up Approach, will support the Exploitation Plan and the Roadmap for Market uptake.

NET-Fuels exploitation activities are focused on the stakeholders’ engagement, partners’ contacts and collaboration with national and European associations and organisations. WP6 Task T6.4 receives inputs from WP5-T5.2 and benefit from the market intelligence research analysis performed in WP5-T5.1, which aims to support the project’s business development definition and its sustainable scale-up approach at industrial level. T6.4 will also benefit from the outcomes of WP5-T5.2 (Business model development) and WP4-T4.4 (socioeconomic analysis).

For more details about the preliminary way defines NET-Fuels Roadmap to Exploitation and Market Uptake, we reproduce and update in the sequel the 4 sub-sections (5.5.1-5.5.4) from D6.2 [8], which describe how the exploitation of the project in relation to its Market Scale-up Roadmap, incorporates the contributions of all defined tasks in WP5.

5.5.1 Competitive Research and Technology & Market Analysis

The NET-Fuels Competitive Research Technology and Market Analysis are dealt within WP5 tasks T5.1 and T5.2. For the **Competitive Research Technology Analysis**, WP5-Task T5.1 conducts an extensive research analysis to position the NET-Fuels technology, in order to support the project's business development definition and its sustainable scale-up approach at the industrial level. For this, relevant competitive

⁹ https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en

technologies, such as CCUS, soil carbon sequestration, energy storage, and negative biofuel activities, related to the value proposition defined for NET-Fuels, are seen as the main focus of the Competitive Research and Technology Analysis (see Figure 28). The “Technology-Watch” living document produced in T5.1 was made available in the project Sharepoint repository in early 2023.

WP5-T5.1: Market & Competitive Research

Tech-Watch Filtering

Eligibility Criteria
For an input to be processed further, the following criteria **must** be met:

Figure 28: NET-Fuels Tech-Watch Filtering Criteria.

WP5-T5.1: Market & Competitive Research

Tech-Watch Database

Project Name	Nation	Sector	Type	Status	Funding	Description	Keywords	Feeds
NET-Fuels	EU	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	3308	NET-Fuels is a 4-year project funded by the European Commission	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, Hydrogen/H ₂ , SCL, Biochar, Methane/CH ₄	Lignocellulose, Forests
HydroFuel	EU	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2822	Hydro-FUEL is a project funded by Horizon 2020 EU's new	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, Biochar	Sewage Sludge
Stenlenset	Belgium	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	2624	The process for ethanol production at the steel mill is	BioFuel, CCUS	Industry Waste
The Ball Bay Project	Australia	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	2628	AREL Energy is developing its first green methanol project	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, Hydrogen/H ₂ , Methanol, Methanol Synthesis, Drop in Fuel	Forestry Residue
HR Global	Spain	B-Fuels	Company	Completed and in operation	2821	We use renewable energy to produce green hydrogen via Synthetic Gasoline. Produced with the SAC technology from	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, hydrogen/H ₂ , CCUS, PFD/PTG, DAC, BE, Drop in Fuel, e-Fuel, SAF/BAF, CCUS, PFD/PTG, Drop in Fuel, e-Fuel	Waste CO ₂ , Atmospheric CO ₂
bioing®	Germany	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2813	bioing® is one answer searching for high quality BE ₂ fuels or fuel	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, CO ₂ , BE, Drop in Fuel	Lignocellulose, Forestry Residue, Farming Residue
BioFFuel	Holland	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2821	biovent and its partners have just successfully completed the first	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, SAF/BAF, FT-Fuel, BE	Lignocellulose, Forestry Residue, Farming Residue
Fulcrum Bio Energy	USA	Biofuels	Company	Completed and in operation	2821	Fulcrum has developed and is operating a proprietary, patented	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, SAF/BAF, FT-Fuel, CCUS, BE, Drop in Fuel	Household Waste
BayouFuels	USA	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	2821	The Bayou Fuels biorefinery will produce sustainable aviation fuel	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, SAF/BAF, FT-Fuel, CCUS, SCL, BE, Drop in Fuel	Lignocellulose, Forestry Residue, Farming Residue
Carbovent	EU	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	2926	The EU funded CARBON project will develop novel technologies	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, CO ₂ , BE, Drop in Fuel	Household Waste
IngolexLife	Netherlands	Biofuels	Company	Completed and in operation	2821	The most distinctive asset of our patented technology is the	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, CO ₂ , SCL, Biochar, BE	Lignocellulose, Forestry Residue, Farming Residue
CO2MTH	EU	Biofuels	Project	Completed	3001	The production of Biofuels from solid biomass involves several	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, FT-Fuel, CCUS, SCL, Biochar, BE	Farming Residue
AgBioIn	Australia	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	N/A	AgBioIn is an Australia first innovation project that will bring	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, FT-Fuel, CCUS, SCL, Biochar, BE	Farming Residue
RED ROCK Biofuels	USA	Biofuels	Company	Cancelled	2821	Red Rock Biofuels was founded in 2013 to tackle the growing need	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioEthanol, SAF/BAF, FT-Fuel	Forestry Residue
Athabasca	UK	Biofuels	Project	Ongoing	2828	We are developing plans to build the first commercial scale waste-	SAF/BAF, CO ₂ , Recycling	Household Waste
Project Liberty	USA	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2804	Project LIBERTY, HDS-DSM's new biorefinery in Emmetsburg, Iowa	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, Ethanol, BE	Farming Residue
Indian River Bioenergy Center	USA	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2883	In July 2023, the Indian River Bioenergy Center has	BIOCCU/BECCUS, Ethanol	Farming Residue
FLOROM	EU	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2801	The vision is to create a process for optimal use of the seasonal	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, FT-Fuel, PFD/PTG, BE, e-Fuel	Farming Residue
Chesapeake BioRefinery	Italy	Biofuels	Project	Completed and in operation	2893	The plant in Chesapeake has a	BIOCCU/BECCUS, BioFuel, CO ₂ , Ethanol	Forestry Residue, Farming Residue

Figure 29: NET-Fuels Database with Tech-Watch Filtered Sources.

Database Features

Figure 30: NET-Fuels filtered Tech-Watch Database Features.

The approach to perform the research analysis has led to the following work-procedures:

- Definition of specific keywords to conduct the search.
- Identification of relevant sources (e.g.: projects, articles) via various repositories and databases for scientific publications and projects (e.g.: BASE, CORDIS).
- Identification of relevant patents and technologies with the help of specialized databases (Esp@cenet, [EUIPO](#), [WIPO](#), etc.).
- Identification of the state of the art in science and technology as well as scientific breakthroughs and industrial pioneers.
- Learning from success cases and from failed projects, from which the reasons for failure can serve as risk mitigation measures for the project.
- Implementation of a “Technology-Watch” living document shared with project partners.
- Filtering of the technologies found w.r.t. the similarities with the NET-Fuels project.
- Creation of a Database with the filtered “Technology-Watch” NET-Fuels comparable technologies, including appropriate searching options to facilitate its use within the NET-Fuels context.

Through this transparent approach for the elaboration of the technology watch (see Figures 28, 29 and 30), the partners are able to interact with the living document available in the project’s repository, updating their contribution of inputs and relevant comments.

Considering the **Market Analysis for NET-Fuels** project, an approach has been developed within WP5 by REACH considering the Products (PRs) and Key-Exploitable Results (KERs), combined with the competitive technologies directly related to them, so that potential risks related to the KERs can be identified and strategies to overcome them can be timely provided.

The approach taken for the initial NET-Fuels market analysis will provide useful information for the Exploitation Strategy defined for NET-Fuels, in the following way (see also Figures 31, 32, and 33):

- Performance of a SWOT Analysis [4] of each relevant competitive technology in comparison with the NET-Fuels technology, considering factors that are internal (strengths and weaknesses) and external (opportunities and threats). This analysis will provide important input for defining the NET-Fuels technology market position, in the face of the identified potential competitors.
- Performance of an external task environment-based Porter’s 5 Forces Analysis, for addressing Competition x Profitability of the project results.

- Performance of a PESTEL Analysis¹⁰ (also called PESTLE¹¹ with original concept described in [3]) will provide an overview of the macro-environmental factors, namely: Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental, that may have an influence in the NET-Fuels market analysis. As a strategic tool for understanding market growth/decline as well as business position, PESTEL will be especially useful in this analysis to identify potential markets.

Figure 31: Methodology Pathway to the NET-Fuels Market Competitive Research Analysis (i).

Market & Competitive Research Analysis (MCRA)

INTERNAL:

- SWOT Analysis: Strengths and Weaknesses

EXTERNAL (Task environment):

- SWOT Analysis: Threats and Opportunities
- Porter's 5 Forces (Competition x Profitability): Competitors, Suppliers, Distributors, Customers, Strategic Partners

MACRO ENVIRONMENT:

- PESTEL Analysis: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal

Figure 32: Methodology Pathway to the NET-Fuels Market Competitive Research Analysis (ii).

¹⁰ PESTEL: <https://www.professionalacademy.com/blogs/marketing-theories-pestel-analysis/>

¹¹ PESTLE: <https://libguides.library.usyd.edu.au/c.php?g=508107&p=5994242>

Market & Competitive Research Analysis (MCRA)

Figure 33: Contributions to the NET-Fuels Market Competitive Research Analysis.

Overall, during the reporting period for D6.3, REACH has developed the following efforts towards the **Market Analysis for NET-Fuels**:

- In order to facilitate use and understanding, the Technology Watch has been updated: new and more distinguishable keywords were added and applied, inputs were evaluated and labelled according to their relevance to the project, and information has been adapted to the essentials for maximum readability.
- Eligibility criteria for filtering the inputs were also created. For an input from the Tech-Watch list to be processed further, relevant criteria must be met, like: comparable Feedstock; Fuel as output; and Carbon neutrality or negativity.
- A Database with all filtered inputs from the Tech-Watch list was developed, with searching options to facilitate its use.
- The SWOT Analysis of the NET-Fuels technology and some of the most relevant competitive technologies has already started to be carried out and it is expected to be concluded in March 2024.
- REACH has also conducted virtual meetings in January and February 2024 with Fraunhofer and UNIBO to discuss some methodologies that will be applied in the Market Research Analysis, like Porter's Five Forces and PESTEL Analysis. The Figure to follow illustrates one of those meetings.

Figure 34: REACH organized session about PESTEL Analysis.

5.5.2 Business Models and Business Plans

In NET-Fuels the creation of Business Models and Business Plans is dealt within WP5-T5.2. Business Models (BM) are planned for exploiting the Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Business Models Canvas (BMC) [5], in their Sustainable Version [6], will be used to design BMs for each KER. The BMC embeds: the value proposition (value proposition and sustainability benefits), customers (customer relationships, channels, customer segments, beneficiaries), financial model (cost structure, revenue streams), and capabilities (key activities, key partners, key resources). Due to its simplicity, it will allow the partners to visualize the most important aspects of their developed products in relation to their business potential.

The definition of the Business Models will provide essential information for the overall Business Plan development of the project and will provide significative inputs for the exploitation activities of the project, also taking into consideration aspects of NET-Fuels' socio-economic analysis (WP4-T4.4).

KERs Individual Exploitation Plans: As a consequence of the KERs Business Models, Individual Exploitation Plans will be defined for the selected Key Exploitable Results shown in Figure 14. This task will demand intensive interaction with the involved NET-Fuels project partners, since each partner has different goals and perspectives for their developed products within the project, the potential project's advances, services, know-how, and work experience.

NET-Fuels Business Plan: A Business Plan (BP) will be developed for the overall common KER related to the developed NET-Fuels technology, to showcase the business potential of the technology and to define the tactics to achieve the defined goals. The Business Plan development will take into consideration all the relevant information from the market and competitive research analysis (potential market size, competitive technologies), and from the NET-Fuels overall common Business Model (potential end-users, cost structure, channels). NET-Fuels BP will also assess the project's results (development status, potential impact, innovation potential, IPR issues) and social and economic impacts. An analysis of the level of competition in the negative biofuels industry will be conducted to determine how its long-term profitability is affected. Hence, the Business Plan will bring preliminary commercialization strategies, risk assessment and financial projections to the project.

During the reporting period for D6.3, the confirmation of the Key Exploitable Results was made within the 1st Internal Exploitation Workshop in October 2023, which represents the first step for the Business Model and Business Plan development. Literature review is being conducted and a first draft of the Business Model Canvas for NET-Fuels is in development.

5.5.3 Regulatory Assessment

The regulatory framework for the project scale-up process will be assessed within WP5-T5.3 (led by UNIBO), taking into account the market research analysis scope. A list of requirements and priorities will be defined, related to methane grid injection, biochar certification, industrial emissions, water management, among others.

Project specific plant configurations may also require further investigation, for instance, in hydrogen storage and compression, incentives and schemes in specific countries or geographic areas.

A database or document will be compiled, considering input management (regulations and requirements to handle the feedstock, end-of-waste), processing (e.g., emission limit levels), product quality (e.g., H₂ standards, biochar certification), type of legislation, jurisdiction, subject/field of application, risks and barrier and carbon accounting (both for the process and for the use of biochar in soils for carbon sequestration).

Also in WP5- Task T5.3, implementation will be followed, and interventions made where needed to examine specific problems and issues. A dedicated session or joint consortium meeting session will be organized to present the findings (M5.4, M30). (Task to be initiated on M18, April 2024).

5.5.4 System Scale-up Approach

Scale-up strategies of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level will be evaluated by WP5-T5.4, led by FRA. The aim is to provide energy and material balances, industry-scale sizing of major units, estimation of the overall cost, process conversions, energy consumption, and waste stream production.

The results of the operation at pilot scale (WP2 and WP3) will serve to analyze process parameters and yields as a basis to estimate the cost efficiency of the process. These data sets will be joined with process and operational data provided from industrial partners like refineries. Then, concepts for scale-up will be developed, consisting in the definition of feasible guidelines (a roadmap) for a sustainable scale-up approach at industrial level of the project, and the identification of appropriate and diversified case studies to validate the overall NET-Fuels system. The final cost assessment will serve as input for design optimization in the scale-up phase.

During the reporting period for D6.3, virtual meetings between REACH and Fraunhofer Institute UMSICHT (FRA) took place to initiate cooperation and discussions on WP5-T5.4 (see Figure 35).

Figure 35: Meeting between REACH & FRA members in Dec. 2023.

5.6 Exploitation Management & Monitoring

The exploitation management for NET-Fuels project will follow the defined Exploitation Strategy and will consider several aspects related to: the dissemination of the project results; the identified stakeholders and potential end-users; the interaction among project partners, end-users and stakeholders; the interaction with the NET-Fuels Advisory Board members and their institutions; and the networking procedure to be adopted within this scenario.

The Exploitation Control Mechanism (ECM) to be adopted embeds: (1) the steps of the Exploitation Strategy and its KPIs (still to be further defined); (2) the NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book containing details about the Project Results (PRs) and the KERs; and (3) the Market Scale-up Roadmap and its driving parameters.

According to the EC, the Beneficiaries of the Horizon Europe are responsible for the Exploitation outcomes for at least two years after the end of the project. As the partner responsible for the Exploitation, REACH will monitor the Exploitation Results by keeping track of all activities both during and beyond the lifetime of the project, aligned with the Horizon Results Booster (HRB) requirements. Figure 36 illustrates the preliminary plan for NET-Fuels Exploitation Management and Monitoring.

Figure 36: Preliminary NET-Fuels Exploitation Management & Monitoring Plan.

5.7 Exploitation Concluding Remarks

The main target is that the NET-Fuels Exploitation Strategy will ensure and amplify the impact of the project results to guarantee effective exploitation during and after the lifetime of the project.

The preliminary Exploitation Plan (EP) delivered in month M6 within D6.2 [8], described how the exploitation tasks will be led and structured within NET-Fuels implementation phase, considering: the general exploitation objectives; the initial exploitation strategy; the expected impacts (technical, socio-economic and environmental); the planned tasks and activities; and the initial steps for the intellectual property definition among partners and respective IPR management.

The current document (D6.3 - First Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report) composes the first update on D6.2, aligned with the overall Plan of NET-Fuels Deliverables and lead partners shown in Figure 1. D6.3 updates on the EP in M16. Further updates will follow with D6.4 (Scale-up of the integrated NET-Fuels technology system for industrial level) in M36. Moreover, reports about the dissemination and exploitation activities of the project will be included in the technical parts of the project reports RP1, RP2 and RP3, respectively planned for covering the periods of: RP1 (M1 - M18) with submission on June 2024; RP2 (M19 - M36) with submission on December 2025; and RP3 (M37 - M48) with submission on October 2026, as defined in [1,2].

6 Conclusions

This document represents the 1st Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Report (D6.3) of the NET-Fuels project with respect to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities and tasks of the project. This has the aim of maximising impact, whilst creating pathways to follow-up developments and collaborations to take the technology to pre-commercial scale and, ultimately, commercial adoption. This deliverable represents the first DEC report after D6.2 [8]. The DEC activities will be updated at least annually as new information and opportunities arise.

7 References

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Gantt Chart 2a: Updated Short-term communication and dissemination plan to end of 2024

This Gantt chart will be discussed with project partners over the course of 2024 and refined and updated as necessary.

Short-term DC&E Plan (to end 2024)

Top Level Activity	Task	Partner inputs	2024													
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec		
Meeting with Partners	Project meetings	All														
	Review stakeholder list to identify key engagement targets for 2024	WRG, REACH, UniBo														
	Finalise engagement strategies for 2024	WRG, REACH, UniBo														
Website and Digital Media	Review and update website	All: Requirements and feedback														
	Update flyers/posters for upcoming conferences	All: Feedback and comments														
	Create project brochure for conferences	All: Feedback and comments														
	Storyboard for new motion graphics/infographics video	All: Feedback and comments														
	Create motion graphics/infographics video	All: Sign off of final video														
	Create technical articles for website	N/A														
	Project newsletters	All: Input on content, feedback, and sign-off														
Conferences and Events	Define events for NETFuels participation	All: Review partner presentations/publications (if applicable)														
	NET-Fuels attendance at conferences (current planned)	As required: Attendance														
Publications and papers	Define journals and magazines for publishing articles	All: Review publication														

Gantt Chart 2b: Short-term updated exploitation plan to end of 2023-2024

Top Level Specific Exploitation Activities	Tasks	Partner inputs	2023				2024				
			7/8	9/10	11 / 12	13/14	15/16	17 /18	19 / 20	20 / 21	
			May June	July Aug	Sept. Oct.	Nov, Dec,	Jan. Feb	Mar April	May June	July Aug.	
	Months										
NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book	The NET-Fuels Exploitation Living Check-book will be made available via the NET-Fuels SharePoint for receiving inputs about PRs, KERs, BGs + ESAB updates	All – Feedback and guided input (from M7 onwards)									
NET-Fuels Common KER Identification	Workshop on Common KER - Product (PR) and Key Exploitation Results (KER) Identification	All – Attendance & Feedback (initially estimated for M12)									
NET-Fuels Individual KERs Identification	Workshop on Individual KERs - Product (PRs) and Key Exploitation Results (KERs) Identification	All – Attendance & Feedback (initially estimated for M11)									
NET-Fuels Intellectual Property Definition	Workshop on Intellectual Property Definition & Management of IPR for NET-Fuels PRs& KERs	All – Attendance & Feedback (initially estimated for M13)									
NET-Fuels KERs Business Models	Discussions & Virtual Meetings with Partners for preliminary definition of KERs Business Models	All – Requirements and Feedback (estimated to start on 2023 M14)									
Interaction with ESAB Members & NET-Fuels	ESAB selected stakeholders dedicated meetings with NET-Fuels partners for the definition Business Plans	REACH, UNIBO & Selected Partners (estimated to start on 2023 M13)									

Annex 3: NET-Fuels Living Check-book – Individual Key Exploitable Results

Key Exploitable Result	Description of the Key Exploitable Result	Key Deliverables	Key Milestones	Key Deliverables	Key Milestones	Key Deliverables	Key Milestones	Key Deliverables
A. NET-Fuels Assessment Framework (JUNAC)	Multi-stakeholder bodies, 30-35 members	Commonly agreed definitions						
B. Thermo-chemical conversion system at TRL 5 (FKA)	Thermo-chemical conversion system at TRL 5 (FKA)							
C. Clean CO ₂ from syngas (FKA)	Clean CO ₂ from syngas (FKA)							
D. Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)	Bio-steam chemical methanation (BEM) at TRL 5 (FKA)
E. Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)	Pilot BEM reactor integrated with TCR and syngas processes (SICAT)
F. CH ₄ routes of conversion (SICAT)	CH ₄ routes of conversion (SICAT)							
G. Carbon sink certification guidelines (TMAA)	Carbon sink certification guidelines (TMAA)							